

Catalytic Effect of Aluminium Oxide in Ester Saponification Reactions

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Manuscript received 13 February 1991, revised 20 October 1992, accepted 2 December 1992

The influence of mineral particle surface on the hydrolytic breakdown of organic pollutants in water has become a subject of increasing interest. Certain hydrolytic reactions have been reported to take place at faster rates in interfacial regions of solvents with air, micelle, solids etc. Terephthalic acid esters which hydrolyse slowly under neutral or alkaline conditions, have been found to react faster in the presence of alumina particles¹. In a preliminary study we have found that benzhydryl hydrogen phthalate when subjected to saponification reaction, hydrolysed faster in the presence of suspended alumina². Adsorption and consequent catalytic effect seems to be the cause for the enhancement in the reaction rates.

Results and Discussion

Acid phthalic esters of methanol, benzyl alcohol and 1-phenylethanol and methyl acetate have been

subjected to alkaline hydrolysis in the presence of alumina. The ester anions in the case of the acid phthalates react with the hydroxide ions according to second order kinetic rate law. The specific rates at various temperatures for the normal and the alumina-catalysed reactions are presented in Table 1.

It is seen that there is significant rate enhancement when these reactions take place in the presence of suspended alumina particles. Rate enhancement for hydrolytic reactions at interfaces of solvents with solids, micelle and ion-exchange resin³ can be attributed to an increase in the interaction of the reactants at the interface. In the case of solid solvent interfaces, adsorption of the reactants at sites of the solid can increase their concentration and modify the energetic requirements for the reaction. Studies on the adsorption on alumina of the anion of the acid phthalic ester of benzhydryl have shown that adsorption takes place to the

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATES AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF SOME ACID PHTHALIC ESTERS AND METHYL ACETATE WITH AND WITHOUT THE PRESENCE OF SUSPENDED ALUMINA

Solvent : Aqueous 20% dioxane, [ester]=0.02 M, alumina : 10 g dm⁻³, [NaOH]*=0.05 M

Substrate	10 ³ k (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)						Activation parameters					
	Normal			Catalysed			E _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔH [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔS [‡] (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	
	38°	45°	50°	38°	45°	50°	Nor.	Cat.	Nor.	Cat.	Nor.	Cat.
Methyl hydrogen phthalate	3.88	6.16	8.18	6.38	8.42	10.52	51.3	35.5	48.7	32.9	-135	-182
Benzyl hydrogen phthalate	2.56	4.96	8.54	3.31	5.98	10.00	83.2	77.1	80.7	74.5	-36	-53
1-Phenylethyl hydrogen phthalate	1.04	1.53	2.20	1.72	2.45	2.97	53.2	36.8	50.6	34.2	-140	-188
Methyl acetate	23.40	—	—	31.23	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

*[NaOH]=0.03 M with methyl acetate.

extent of about 20% under the experimental conditions. Alumina has a reported⁴ surface area of $82 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and a surface site density of $5.3 \text{ sites nm}^{-2}$. The $-\text{COO}^-$ group can specifically adsorb on to alumina resulting in enhancement in the rates of the hydrolytic reactions. It is also found that alumina increases the rate of hydrolysis of methyl acetate (Table 1).

Excellent linear fits for Arrhenius plots were obtained in all cases (Fig. 1). Energies of activation and entropies of activation for the normal and the catalysed reactions have been determined (Table 1). Normally the surface adsorption in catalysis reduces the activation energy and promotes the rates of reactions. The activation energy is lowered by about 16 kJ in the case of methyl hydrogen phthalate. This is quite a significant reduction in the activation energy. Similar is the case with 1-phenylethyl hydrogen phthalate. However, the reduction in activation energy for benzyl hydrogen phthalate is not appreciable.

Fig. 1. Arrhenius plots for the normal (dotted line) and alumina catalysed (bold line) saponification of (\square) methyl hydrogen phthalate, (\triangle) benzyl hydrogen phthalate and (\circ) 1-phenylethyl hydrogen phthalate.

The entropy of activation values are more negative for the catalysed reaction indicating formation of a more restricted transition state. The entropy

of activation in the case of methyl hydrogen phthalate and 1-phenylethyl hydrogen phthalate are lowered by about 50 J K^{-1} . Such a large reduction in activation entropy arises from formation of a more ordered transition state. This can happen when the transition state is formed by the ester and hydroxide ion that are adsorbed on adjacent sites of alumina surface. Thus the activation entropy values strongly suggest involvement of alumina surface in producing enhancement of rate. The binding of the ester entity on the surface of alumina can cause a diminution in the degrees of freedom of movement and the restriction in this case seems to work favourably for an increased interaction with the hydroxide ions present either on active sites or in the adjacent diffuse layer to give a faster reaction velocity.

Experimental

Acid phthalic esters of methanol, benzyl alcohol and 1-phenylethanol⁶ were purified through their sodium salts and by repeated recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. $40-60^\circ$). Methyl acetate (B.D.H.) used was further purified by distillation. AnalaR grade dioxane and sodium hydroxide were used. Double-distilled water was used for preparing aqueous solvents. γ -Alumina (E. Merck) was employed. The reactions were carried out in closed glass vessels at constant temperatures with stirring. The course of the reaction was followed titrimetrically. Kinetic studies in homogeneous conditions were done as usual.

References

1. A. T. STONE and J. COLL, *Interface Sci.*, 1988, **127**, 429.
2. T. D. R. NAIR and W. VARGHESE, "Effect of mineral surface area on the rate of alkaline hydrolysis of acid phthalic ester of benzhydrol", Proceedings of Kerala Science Congress, 1990-91.
3. G. ADAM and M. DELBRUCK in "Structural Chemistry and Molecular Biology", eds. A. RICH and H. DAVIDSON, Freeman, San Francisco, 1968; S. L. HARDT, *Biophys. Chem.*, 1979, **10**, 239.
4. S. H. R. DAVIES, Ph.D. Thesis, California Institute of Technology, 1985.
5. E. L. ELIEL and J. T. KOFRON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4587.